

Thallimetric Oxidations. X. Titrimetric Method for the Determination of Mandelic Acid and Analysis of Binary Mixtures of Mandelic Acid and Hypophosphite and Ternary Mixtures of Mandelic Acid, Oxalic Acid and Hydrogen Peroxide

M. S. PRASADA RAO*, R. KALAVATHI, T. SIVA RAO and P. SUNITA

Bio-Inorganic Chemistry Laboratories, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003

Manuscript received 3 November 1995, revised 26 June 1996, accepted 9 July 1996

Mandelamine is methenamine mandelate, a urinary tract antiseptic that owes its activity to formaldehyde¹, where methenamine is hexamethylenetetraamine. The compound decomposes in water to generate formaldehyde. The mandelic acid used along with the medicine to maintain low pH in the bladder and the renal pelvis, is an active reducing agent and photochemically active. So the redox reactions of mandelic acid and its estimation in the physiological fluids is of importance. Hence, the present investigation on the thermal and photochemical redox reactions of thallium(III) with mandelic acid was undertaken.

Few redox methods are available for the estimation of mandelic acid. Mandelic acid is determined by allowing it to react with excess of manganese(III) in 9 M acetic acid, the unreacted manganese(III) is back-titrated iodometrically using starch as indicator¹. In another method², mandelic acid is oxidised quantitatively to benzoic acid with an excess of periodate or telluratocuprate(III) complex. Nema an Verma³ developed an iodometric method for the determination of mandelic acid. West and Skoog⁴ oxidised mandelic acid by treating with excess of vanadium(V) in sulphuric acid medium. The above methods are indirect determinations and involve laborious procedures. However, we have examined the reaction between thallium(III) and mandelic acid in sulphuric acid medium and have developed a convenient titrimetric method for the determination of mandelic acid.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between thallium(III) and mandelic acid is slow, but is considerably fast at elevated temperatures. Separate studies had shown that mandelic acid does not interfere in the titration of thallium(I) with bromate using methyl orange as indicator. So the reaction is used to monitor the progress of the reaction. The thermal oxidation of mandelic acid in perchloric acid medium is avoided so as to exclude the possibility of any explosion. Thermally mandelic acid is oxidised to benzaldehyde by thallium(III), which is confirmed by the general spot test for aldehyde groups. The stoichiometric ratio of thallium(III) to mandelic acid is found to be 1 : 1,

However, a minimum of six-fold excess of thallium(III) to mandelic acid is required for the quick progress of the reaction but still higher concentrations do not appear to increase the rate of the reaction very much. The use of halides as catalysts in thallimetric oxidation reactions has been reported⁶. So bromide and chloride were tested as catalysts. It was found that at higher temperatures (~80° and above), bromide itself reduces thallium(III) to thallium(I). So its effect on the thermal oxidation of mandelic acid could not be studied. But, chloride, even at low concentrations, retards the reaction between mandelic acid and thallium(III). Further, the increase in acid concentration also decreased the rate of the oxidation.

The result of the present titrimetric method of determination of mandelic acid (0.050–0.25 mmol) using thermal activation environment is in good agreement with the quantity taken, RSD = 0.54%.

Analysis of binary mixtures of mandelic acid and hypophosphite : Bromide catalyses the photochemical oxidation of hypophosphite by thallium(III)⁷. Even though the photochemical oxidation of mandelic acid by thallium(III) does not correspond to any definite product, the reaction is completely stopped in high chloride media. But mandelic acid is thermally oxidised to benzaldehyde and hypophosphite to phosphate⁷ by thallium(III). Hence, the thallium(I) formed during the thermal oxidation of the mixture corresponds to the conversion of mandelic acid to benzaldehyde and hypophosphite to phosphate. The thallium(I) is determined bromatometrically as mandelic acid and hypophosphite does not interfere in this method.

Hypophosphite alone can be determined⁸ by oxidising to phosphite by treating with a known excess of chloramine-T in sulphuric acid medium for 24 h at room temperature. Under these conditions mandelic acid remains unaltered. Then the excess chloramine-T is determined iodometrically. The amount of chloramine-T consumed corresponds to the hypophosphite present in the mixture and the concentration of mandelic acid can be computed from the above data. Based on these observations the opti-

imum conditions for the analysis of the mixtures of mandelic acid and hypophosphite are established.

In the recommended procedure, a solution containing 0.05–0.25 mmol each of mandelic acid and hypophosphite, 5.0 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid (7.5 ml) and thallium(III) (2.5 mmol) was diluted to 75 ml and refluxed for 8 h. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 ml) and 0.1% methyl orange indicator (0.1 ml) were then added, it was cooled to 60° and titrated with 0.05 *N* potassium bromate solution (1.392 g dm⁻³). The titre (a) corresponds to the total concentration of mandelic acid and twice that of hypophosphite. To a second aliquot of the mixture, 3.6 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (10 ml) and chloramine-T (1.0 mmol) were added and it was kept at room temperature for 24 h. Then the excess chloramine-T was determined iodometrically. The amount of chloramine-T consumed (b) corresponds to the concentration of hypophosphite. Then the amount of mandelic acid corresponds to (a-2b) mmol and that of hypophosphite to b mmol. Typical results are presented in Table 1.

Analysis of ternary mixtures of mandelic acid, oxalic acid and hydrogen peroxide: Chloride and bromide at low

concentrations catalyse the photochemical oxidation of oxalic acid by thallium(III)⁹. But bromide in low concentrations catalyses the photochemical oxidation of hydrogen peroxide with thallium(III), while chloride inhibits the reaction¹⁰. Based on this selective oxidation of hydrogen peroxide and oxalic acid by thallium(III) under different conditions, a method was described for the analysis of mixtures of oxalic acid and hydrogen peroxide¹¹. Moreover, chloride catalyses the photochemical oxidation of oxalic acid and inhibits the oxidation of mandelic acid and hydrogen peroxide. It was also reported that Fe^{II} in very small concentrations catalyses the photochemical oxidation of hydrogen peroxide by thallium(III) even in high chloride media¹², and under these conditions mandelic acid and oxalic acid remain unaltered. On the basis of these observations, a convenient differential titrimetric method is described for the analysis of ternary mixtures containing mandelic acid, oxalic acid and hydrogen peroxide, and the results are summarised in Table 2.

Interferences: Mn^{II} does not interfere in the photochemical and thermal reactions of mandelic acid with Tl^{III}, while Ce^{IV} and Cu^{II} interfere. Bromide interferes with the thermal reduction while inhibits the photochemical reaction. Chloride inhibits both the thermal and photochemical reactions.

Experimental

Thallium(III) solutions were prepared by dissolving thallium(III) hydroxide (obtained by oxidising Tl^{III}-sulphate with bromine, precipitating with NH₄OH and washing free from halides) in perchloric acid and sulphuric acid, and standardised bromatometrically after reduction to thallium(I) as reported earlier¹³. An aqueous solution of mandelic acid (E. Merck) was prepared and standardised¹⁴.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF BINARY MIXTURES OF MANDELIC ACID AND HYPHOSPHITE

Binary mixtures taken (mmol)		Determined results (mmol)	
Mandelic acid	Hypophosphite mmol	Mandelic acid	Hypophosphite mmol
0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050
0.060	0.100	0.060	0.099
0.080	0.150	0.079	0.149
0.100	0.075	0.099	0.075
0.150	0.200	0.150	0.199
0.200	0.250	0.200	0.250
0.250	0.175	0.248	0.175

TABLE 2—CONDITIONS FOR THE ANALYSIS OF TERNARY MIXTURES OF MANDELIC ACID, OXALIC ACID AND HYDROGEN PEROXIDE

[Tl^{III}] = 2.5 mmol; Tl^I formed is determined bromatometrically

Composition of the mixture, 0.05–0.25 mmol each	Concentration of acid (mol dm ⁻³)		Catalyst (mmol)		Time of exposure h	Oxidations effected	Amount of Tl ^I formed mmol
	H ₂ SO ₄	HClO ₄	Cl ⁻	Fe ²⁺			
Mandelic acid + oxalic acid + hydrogen peroxide	0.5				8.00	Mandelic acid to benzaldehyde Oxalic acid to CO ₂ + H ₂ O Hydrogen peroxide to H ₂ O + O ₂	a
Mandelic acid + oxalic acid + hydrogen peroxide		1.0	25		2.30	Oxalic acid to CO ₂ + H ₂ O Mandelic acid and Hydrogen peroxide are unaffected	b
Mandelic acid + oxalic acid + hydrogen peroxide		1.0	75	3 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.00	Hydrogen peroxide to H ₂ O + O ₂ Mandelic acid and Oxalic acid are unaffected	c

*Calculation: Amount of mandelic acid = a - (b + c) mmol, amount of oxalic acid = b mmol, amount of H₂O₂ = c mmol

An aqueous solution of sodium hypophosphite (AnalaR) was standardised¹⁵.

All the work was done with a Philips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (200/250V, 125W) as the light source, placed 15 cm above the test solutions contained in colourless uncovered glass vessels.

Titrimetric determination of mandelic acid :

Thermal method : To an aliquot containing 0.05–0.25 mmol of mandelic acid were added 5.0 M H₂SO₄ (5.0 ml) and thallium(III) sulphate (1.5 mmol), it was diluted to 50 ml and refluxed for 6 h. Then concentrated HCl (10 ml) was added, cooled to 60°, 0.1% methyl orange indicator (0.1 ml) added and titrated the thallium(I) formed with 0.05 N potassium bromate until the indicator is destroyed.

The series of experiments conducted on the photochemical oxidation of mandelic acid by thallium(III), by varying the concentrations of thallium(III), acid (HClO₄ and H₂SO₄), chloride and bromide, show that the stoichiometry of the reaction could not correspond to any particular product and photochemical oxidation of mandelic acid does not stop at any definite stage. Because of this, it is not possible to utilise the thallimetric photochemical oxidation of mandelic acid for analytical purposes.

Determination of Tl^{III} (mmol range) :

The principle of the method is similar to the one described for the determination of mandelic acid. The thermal and photochemical procedures can be applied for a quantitative determination of thallium(III) using excess mandelic acid. The time required for thermal reduction of thallium(III) is 20 min and for photochemical reduction 10 min. The photochemical reaction can be utilised for the estimation of thallium(III) because in the presence of excess of mandelic the reaction stops at benzaldehyde stage.

Thallium(III) (0.050–0.500 mmol) was estimated by the present method of reduction to thallium(I) using mandelic acid and environment for photoactivation and thermal activation. The results are in good agreement with RSD 1.7% and 0.6% respectively.

Procedure :

To an aliquot containing 0.05–0.25 mmol each of mandelic acid, oxalic acid and H₂O₂ were added 5.0 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (7.5 ml) and Tl^{III} (2.5 mmol), it was diluted to 75 ml and refluxed for 8 h. Then concentrated HCl (15 ml) and 0.1% methyl orange indicator (0.1 ml) were added, it was cooled to 60° and titrated with 0.05 N potassium bromate (1.392 g dm⁻³). The titre corresponded to the total

TABLE 3—ANALYSIS OF TERNARY MIXTURES OF MANDELIC ACID, OXALIC ACID AND HYDROGEN PEROXIDE (TITRIMETRIC METHOD, mmol RANGE)*

Ternary mixtures taken (mmol)			Determined results (mmol)		
M.A.	O.A.	H.P.	M.A.	O.A.	H.P.
0.050	0.100	0.150	0.050	0.099	0.150
0.100	0.150	0.200	0.099	0.149	0.200
0.150	0.200	0.250	0.150	0.198	0.248
0.200	0.250	0.050	0.198	0.248	0.050
0.250	0.050	0.100	0.248	0.050	0.100

*M.A. = Mandelic acid, O.A. = oxalic acid, H.P. = hydrogen peroxide.

concentration of mandelic acid, oxalic acid and H₂O₂. To a second aliquot of the mixture were added 5.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid (15 ml) and chloride (25 mmol) and the mixture was exposed to the light source for 3 h. The titre obtained by adopting the earlier procedure corresponded to the amount of H₂O₂ only. The individual concentrations were computed from these values. Procedure for the analysis of these mixtures and typical results obtained by adopting these procedures are given in Tables 2 and 3.

References

1. M. K. WADHAWA and S. BOSE, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1972, **52**, 106.
2. S. BOSE and NAIR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 505.
3. S. N. NEMA and R. M. VERMA, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 400.
4. D. M. WEST and D. A. SKOOG, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 583.
5. K. EGRIL, *Dtsch. Apoth-ztg*, 1980, **120**, 1416.
6. S. R. SAGI, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1993, **280**, 299.
7. M. S. P. RAO, A. R. M. RAO, K. V. RAMANA and S. R. SAGI, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1993, **71**, 801.
8. A. S. KOMAROWSKY, W. F. FILONOWA and I. M. KORENMAN, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1934, **96**, 321.
9. S. R. SAGI, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1983, **61**, 2795.
10. M. S. P. RAO, A. R. M. RAO, K. V. RAMANA and S. R. SAGI, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 753.
11. M. S. P. RAO and A. R. M. RAO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **242**, 229.
12. P. D. SHARMA and Y. K. GUPTA, *Talanta*, 1973, **20**, 903.
13. S. R. SAGI, G. S. P. RAJU, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 413; A. R. M. RAO, M. S. P. RAO, K. V. RAMANA and S. R. SAGI, *Talanta*, 1989, **36**, 686.
14. P. GUPTA, P. D. SHARMA and Y. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 392.
15. D. N. BERNHART, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1798.